

TEXT DIVISION IN TRANSLATION UNITS

ZIYOTOVA RA'NO UTKIR KIZI

(Student of SamSIFL)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7905645>

Annotation: this article is devoted to that in contrast to abbreviated, full translation aims to completely reproduce all the components of the information order of the source text in the units of the target language. Full translation can be done in different ways, but the following can be considered the most common: literal or verbatim translation, semantic and communicative translation.

Key words: sentence, language, activity, transferring, definitions, stylistic, source text

One of the basic skills of a translator is to be familiar with different ways of dividing the source text.

The most common mistake of novice translators is the desire to translate verbatim, that is, to monotonously divide the source text or statement into individual words, find what corresponds to them in the target language, and thus compose the translated text. The essence of this error is actually replacing the ideas about the nature of the translated signs instead of the speech units to be translated, the translator mechanically replaces the language units, and the linguistic composition in different languages. one or another speech unit may not match. The exact definition of translation units is one of the most important conditions for the accuracy of translation in general. The very concept of "interpretation unit" is somewhat tentative, and scholars disagree about the term itself and the nature of the concept. The most interesting developments in this area are presented in the works of L. S. Barkhudarov and V. N. Komissarov and reduced to the following most general definition: "By a unit of translation we mean such a unit in the source text that this unit can be matched in the text. translated text, but its components do not have correspondence in the translated text separately" [2].

The main unit of translation can be not only a word, but any language unit: from a phoneme to a superphrase unit. The main condition for the correctness of the definition of the source unit to be translated is the definition of the textual function of a certain source unit. The inadequacy of literal translation is precisely related to the incorrect assessment of the textual functions of language units: falling into this or that speech (oral or written) situation, the word is connected as a language unit turns out to be through systematic connections with other words of the given text, i.e. situational dependence or a series of dependences on the terms of the text.

The phenomenon of contextual relations of the word predetermines the spatio-temporal and causal features of the verbal composition of the text, and the expression of these relations can be fundamentally different in different languages. In essence, the translator does not deal with the individual words themselves, but with the system of relationships between words determined by the source text. That is why it is important for the translator to identify and evaluate both individual dependencies and the system of dependencies in general. For example, the message "He lives in St. Petersburg" practically corresponds to the English phrase "He lives in St. Petersburg" in linguistic content. In St. Petersburg, the message "He lives in Astoria" corresponds to a completely different lexico-grammatical complex. In the second example, trying to follow a word-for-word translation from Russian to English would lead to message distortion, since in this case the unit of translation should be set at the word

level, not at the level of individual words. the level of expressions that determine specific spatio-temporal and causal investigative relationships in the entire range of speech. If in Russian "jite" can be included in the combination of "living in the village" and "living in a hotel", that is, it has a wider field of spatio-temporal applications, then in English these messages require. different language units. In the first case, the text sets the parameters of "permanent residence in a certain place" to the phrase, that is, it introduces a broad spatial connection without a clear temporal connection, which corresponds to the denotative possibilities of the word.

The absence of a strict temporal connection allows us to be satisfied with the simple aspectual form "lives" in translation. In the second example, the text shows a stricter spatial relation "living in a special room" and an even stricter temporal relation "temporary residence", which requires the use of a completely different word in English ("to stay"). A common mistake of temporal explanation ("remaining") is underestimating these connections, which leads to an incomplete translation of "He lives in Astoria", the original meaning of which is approximately the same as the Russian "He lives permanently". will come. Astoria.

The most common mistake in evaluating this group of relationships is trying to translate a direct sequence of characters; in such cases, even the correct structure of the compounds turns out to be insufficient, because the unit to be translated must be a higher-level syntactic structure - often the whole sentence, methods and functions in terms of its real division. English and Russian are not compatible.

A sentence does not necessarily constitute an independent unit of the text: it can be included in more complex superphrase units, the linguistic properties of which depend to some extent on the whole, and this dependence requires different linguistic solutions in different languages. If a word depends on a set of text components, then the translation unit must be based on the entire source text. In addition to in-text patterns, there are extra-textual connections that require the translator to have extensive general cultural or specialized knowledge, without which adequate translation is not possible. In some cases, this group of connections predetermines the appearance of transliteration, tracing or translation commentary in the translated text, which is especially important when translating texts related to the details and characteristics of the original culture.

Thus, when distinguishing the basis for the construction of translation units in the original text, it should be evaluated from the point of view of the system of dependencies that determine both the content and the structural-functional characteristics of the words included in it. The division of the original text into translatable units depends both on the general attitude of the translator to the primary and secondary methods of translation, and on the typological differences in the way of expressing the sign relationship in the source and target languages.

References:

1. Бархударов, Л. С. Язык и перевод (Вопросы общей и частной теории перевода) / Л. С. Бархударов. – М. : Междунар. отношения, 1975. – 240 с.
2. Комиссаров, В. Н. Слово о переводе. / В. Н. Комиссаров. – М. : Междунар. отношения, 1973. – 210 с.

3. Қўлдошев Ў. (2023). ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАГИ ФРАЗАЛИ ФЕЪЛЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ТАРЖИМА МАШАҚҚАТЛАРИ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(12), 65-68. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7902159>
4. Қулдошов У. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида конверсивлик ва антонимлик ҳодисаси //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 3 (80). – С. 67-73.
5. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
6. Daminov N. K. Using Interpreting Strategies in Teaching Simultaneous Translation //European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science. – 2022. – Т. 12. – С. 40-47.
7. Daminov N. Using some strategies in simultaneous interpreting process //E3S Web of Conferences. – 2023. – Т. 381. – С. 01104.
8. Kasimova A. N., Rakhmonova G. N. THE USE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AS HEADLINES OF MASS MEDIA //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 153-158.
9. Kasimova A. N., Nurullayeva D. S. H. NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRENDS IN WORD FORMATION (BASED ON TEXTS IN THE MEDIA) //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 130-133.
10. Nosirovna K. A. et al. NEWSPAPER STYLE. THE TRANSLATION ISSUES OF LEXICAL UNITS AND WORD COMBINATIONS IN NEWSPAPER TEXTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 285-287.
11. Xidirovich N. X., Daminov N. Q. SINXRON TARJIMON NUTQIGA QO ‘YILADIGAN TALABLAR //IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 21-27.